

WORK PRODUCTION IN THE ENTERPRISE ADVERTISING ACTIVITIES OF IMPROVING WAYS

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Abstract. *In this article the enterprise of promotional activities, improvement and development, shown stimulating the system to attract customers on short-term measures, based on quick service and affordable quality services to the population, the pr system to help enterprise buyers to become familiar with the trade of certain types of mainly keep out.*

Keywords: *directory advertising services, integration, product, brand, competition, market.*

Introduction. In Uzbekistan, the ongoing socio-economic reforms, the head of state and the implementation of the national program for the production and careful to be clear by the government, by the state and favorable conditions for business creation opportunities, investments, and due to all the economic indicators likely to stimulate development in the country. rates are being monitored.

Today our republic of samarkand region, industry, agriculture, trade, transport and service sector is one of the developed areas. To ensure sustainable growth in all sectors of the economy in the region, deepening of reforms in the social sphere in the field of a positive number, the work is being carried out.

The company at any time, marketing to the serious attention it gives. After all, wholesale a company is, it is always the customers with deals. This marketing with communication constant development by keeps. Your enterprise in business marketing activities of the organization to the position regardless of if you do not remove, enterprise marketing service organization of 4 units basic organizational structure according to the marketing market and product - focused organizational structures is to use. And its structure follows.

The production of the product based on the organizational structure of the enterprise marketing activities allows a better adaptation to market requirements to each one of different products and production technologies, innovative products that have short life cycle and high requirements to produce.

Directory of marketing services market oriented organizational structure - management structure this type of marketing, then the manager of the particular market specific marketing activities in the market, is responsible for the development and implementation of strategies and plans. Marketing services market oriented organizational structure is shown in the following diagram

Studying the concept of marketing activities of the enterprise, the presence of work and his condition was studied. In particular, the company sales and the marketing concept from the targeted use my attention caught. That is, the enterprise of today's day in the wholesale trade with to deal with, unless, the buyer with the relationship further to strengthen, its capabilities to the full satisfaction, marketing on specialists of their work to the attitude boost attention paid. That's in addition to that, digital marketing is the concept of the order of receive to for also applied. Social networks through advertising and discounts announced being.

Research methodology. A systematic approach to the research process, abstract-logical thinking, guruhlash, comparison, analysis was using the choice of the tracking method.

Analysis and results. Today's day of marketing activities to the attention of the escalation as a result of the company's marketing plan to work out and it follows, as has formed.

Also the sale of products produced important marketing is a phenomenon. Also the enlargement of the type of product in the sales process. Each directory in the organization of the sale of the product are required to be able to channel their trade. Channels of trade to possess the goods as the intermediaries in the delivery of production to the consumer the product, the caller participate.

Because in the field of textile products in the republic of basic consumer goods in regard, the improvement of the mechanism of the stimulation of their trade, domestic consumer market, not only filling, but also accelerated the production process, we also will serve.

The production ofh one of the main directions of the ongoing economic reforms in the trade of products of wide layers of the population and in high quality to satisfy the needs of various consumer goods and services of other seeks.

The trade system has to ensure that the brand of the product, at the same time, the quality of the product manufactured, the sales process, consumer demand is the main factor appearance and the form of it. This condition will allow you to coordinate with the modern market requirements in the production process.

Stimulating sale system to attract customers on short-term measures, based operational services.

The pr system is mainly to help the enterprise will serve to introduce you to trade with certain types of buyers.

Marketing and selling the product demand in the formation of the system in practice long-term strategic goals strategic goals are focused on the sale of the system while stimulating closer. Therefore, both the application system ensures the effectiveness of the sales process in relation to each other. Moreover, increasing sales volume demand, which is a key element in the formation of the system plays an important role in advertising.

1-table

Method of forming public opinion, media and advertising directory

Visit of paper	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High quality and professional manner prepared to be should. - Their mother language, English or other foreign language company about detailed contact information provide, you should. - All the staff in the only style prepared visit of paper be should.
Brochures and catalogs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This high quality be should. - A short, educated and visual be should.
Buyers and customers, number of testimonies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Products and services your confidence with recommend up they make should. - Of you, most of the best and most loyal your customer and your customer, well of their top management by. - These reviews on your advertising brochures to be included in should.
Magazines and newspapers for articles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - your company and market leader as a clear definition of need. - Brochures for your quote come and be should. - Jobs to hang put to you should.

	- Your competent your buyers and your customers will be sent to should.
Video material	- Professional in a manner taken be should. - Interesting, educated and to find easy be should. - Is this your brand and your service most of the good qualities display should. - Short, clear and targeted advertising to the idea of able be should.
Web-site	- Content in terms of it 's deep and rich information to be able see easily and remove, attention is to be involved, be should. - Professional manner in preparation and regularly updated should. - E - question-answer exchange with the possibility of available be should. - If you need, online order gives and sold it to get the possibility to be should.

Source: company data, based on the development of students.

In today's competitive conditions in the region and attracting buyers in the trade market study of light industry enterprises is a marketing tool using less, to 'g'rirog'i, such process does not need to. The main products of the enterprise is raw spinning the reason exactly because of its buyers. However, sewing and knitting enterprises not only out to the foreign market, but also for trying to sell the product in the domestic market, the market has been already grasped the need for a very strong complex. Therefore, enterprises that support the activities of the market in the form of a special infrastructure of the country, constitute the development of their activities.

Direct marketing and event marketing activities had to be created for the reason that the new directory is still very poor form. For this reason, we are the leading trade event for the international and local marketing activities in enterprises we have direct and proposals. Looking for Uzbekistan in a many wholesale companies in the activities of direct marketing elements with acquainted, the enterprise has to offer with out I have. Today's day in the company of their communication policy, the full implementation enhances. Company communication policy in the market of goods previously push on measures of implementation increase: advertising campaigns to conduct, intermediaries and consumers to relevant benefits and discounts to give, the product of the sale with the dealing staff encourage;

The enterprise marketing and communications complex development of strategic system marketing tools (for example, direct marketing, advertising) enterprise products, its existing and potential customers or clients with a reputation about thinking (cognitive) exchange to make it easier and its stability providing you, the public with relations and others) is also competing. competitive environment. Marketing manager from work, production and sale of single process into a combined improvements and qualified plan qualities to be able that you require will. Marketing communications is not only specific to a product or service which is hidden needs, identify and them in the appropriate place and time to promote to and in advertising to, but also research and practical prices setting, forecasting and funding, product distribution and combined control out increase the opportunity to gives.

Thomas practitioners working in advertising and brand policy scholar is, successful brands about the brand of the policy of scientific and practical aspects to learn. Brand of any kind, the theory of first place of the brand, the model, the structure, simple I say when, brands placed in the injected through the shelves of a package offered to be should.

In so doing, Thomas own four from the racks consist of a package offer will, it's size as it is referred, bigger stability for. By the way, this reason for this book is "4D marking" as references. These 4 measures are called:

Functional measure (the brand with the associated product or service usefulness with associated).

Social measurement (self-certain of a social group with to become familiar ability refers to).

Ethical measurements (global or local responsibility perception to). It's the brand and its consumers by share seen and ethical values in them into gets.

Cognitive measure (man support the ability to). Simple, I say when, brand, personalized consumer experience to provide a will.

Today's day in developing social networks in our company's brand, previously put in own our power test we can. The reason, today's day in social network each - way place is incomparable. The company in today's day and no how social networks who does not use. For the same reason, Instagram, Telegram, Facebook and YouTube in the network of the company's personal profile, work, and the brand promote to and improvement for the suggestions worked out we have.

Today, the area is considered one of the leading companies in the production of enterprises. Small and large buildings being paid great attention to the construction of the enterprise, the enterprise paid more attention to less production of waste from the use of the product.

Historically and now also as one of the leading network for the country of production and production work to look there. Indeed, the development of social relations and held the place of production in order to meet the needs of the population.

The sphere of regulation and production by the state, the state proceeding from the needs of the population, in order to improve the social situation, through the economic and social policy, legal, administrative, economic help and shows their impact on society without showing the effects of economic activity of the method you need to understand.

The development of the trading activities of the enterprise for the purpose of improvement and we consider it is worthwhile to perform the following tasks:

- the possibility of the use of affordable and quality services to the population, create economic and legal;
- production and other services in the area of process integration and create mechanisms for the development of cooperation;
- production, production and trade of the state by regulated in an effective mechanism of creation;
- consumers rights to protect, which work out of the organization's activities to enable and accelerate;
- enterprise activities in the logistics system improvement;
- sales, after service and show quality increase and their time of services provision and improve;
- social networks on active be and their branding, I promote make

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